

Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of Ammonium Hexachlororhodite

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Thermogravimetric analysis technique has been used in studying the decomposition of ammonium hexachlororhodite in the solid state at different temperatures. The rate-dependent parameters of the compound have been calculated according to the method described previously¹.

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EXPERIMENTAL

The analysis of ammonium hexachlororhodite (Spec. pure, supplied by Johnson Mathey & Co) corresponded to the formula $[(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{RhCl}_6 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. A Stanton thermobalance (high temperature model) was used for thermogravimetric measurements. The rate of heating was maintained at about 2°/min. Temperature was recorded by Pt/Pt-13% Rh thermo-couple. Weight losses were within 2% of the theoretical values.

TABLE I

Compound.	Temp. range of decomposition.	% Yield	
		Theor.	Expt.
$(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{RhCl}_6$	160 — 200°	93.19	94.25
$[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}] \text{Cl}_2$ + RhCl_3	295 — 447°	63.48	61.50
$\text{RhCl}_2 + \text{RhCl}$	468 — 602°	39.35	39.75
Rh_2O_3	1070 — 1120°	32.00	32.50

DISCUSSION

The thermogram (Fig. 1) shows that the water of hydration begins to come out at 160° and continues to 290°. At this point there is a break in the curve corresponding to the anhydrous form $[(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{RhCl}_6]$. At 295°, the anhydrous ammonium hexachloro-

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1. Agarwala and Naik, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1961, 24, 125.

rhodite started decomposing to a mixture of two compounds, $[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ and RhCl_3 , as also reported by Leidie². The reaction was over at 447°, when the two phases, ammoniorhodite and rhodium trichloride, were obtained. Analysis showed that the two components were present in the molecular ratio of 1:1. A horizontal constant-weight region between 447° and 468° was obtained, indicating the stability of these two compounds.

At 468°, a slow reaction was observed which became fairly fast at 618°. Weight-loss analysis corresponds to the decomposition of the above phases to a mixture of RhCl and RhCl_2 in the ratio of 1:1. The reaction was complete at 662°. The thermogram shows that these two chlorides are stable and no thermal decomposition is observed till 1070°.

At 1070°, both the chlorides began to decompose and finally a mixture of rhodium metal and oxide of rhodium was obtained. The reaction was over at 1120° and after this no reaction took place up to 1400°. The weight loss indicates that the bulk of the material is Rh_2O_3 . It may be mentioned that freshly prepared rhodium metal could absorb oxygen from the atmosphere³. The thermogravimetric results obtained are summarised in Table I.

FIG. 1

Calculation of the Rate Parameters.— To evaluate the kinetics of decomposition of the compound by thermogravimetric analysis, the following equation was used:

$$-\frac{E^*}{2.3R} \frac{\Delta(T^{-1})}{\Delta \log W_r} = -x + \frac{\Delta \log (dw/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r}$$

where E^* = activation energy, x = order of reaction, T = absolute temperature, t = time, W_r = wt. loss at completion of reaction - wt. loss up to time t , dw/dt = rate of loss of weight with time, and R = gas constant. A plot of

$$\frac{\Delta \log (dw/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r} \text{ vs } \frac{\Delta(T^{-1})}{\Delta \log W_r}$$

2. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1889, vi, 17, 265.

3. Gutbier *et al.*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1916, 95, 225.

4. Freeman and Carroll, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 304.

was drawn. The order of reaction and the activation energy of dehydration and decomposition of ammonium hexachlororhodite was calculated from the curve (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2

Typical plots of the above equation are shown in Fig. 2 and the results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

	Activation energy.	Order of reaction.
(a) $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{RhCl}_6 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow (\text{NH}_4)_3\text{RhCl}_6 + 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.00 kcal.	0.90
(b) $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{RhCl}_6 \rightarrow [\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2 + \text{RhCl}_3$	36.88	0.65
(c). $[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2 + \text{RhCl}_3 \rightarrow \text{RhCl} + \text{RhCl}_2$	71.66	0.96

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